

The Fourth Industrial Revolution And Persons With Disabilities: Peeping Into The Future Through The Lens Of The Present

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Abstract

The world at large has experienced series of developmental changes through the first, second and third industrial revolutions which have impacted the interaction of human to human as well as human to machines. Through observable process and products, these revolutions were dynamic with an unprecedented effect on all sectors of human development including education. Fortunately, persons with disabilities have being part of these revolutions but not without challenges which is yet to be resolved even in this digital age. Negative societal attitude, inequalities and difficulties in accessing quality education which is digitally motivated have negatively influence how persons with disabilities interact with their society in this present time. Previous studies have bemoaned various barriers to inclusion of persons with disability, recommended models of inclusion in this digital era but how persons with disabilities will cope and function meaningfully in the fourth industrial revolution (Industrie 4.0) remains a mirage. While the fourth industrial revolution is full of promises for improvement in human interaction, there are fears of negative implications as well. Persons without disabilities are skeptical about possible fear of job loss, depression amidst other challenges, persons with disabilities, particularly those in higher learning are still far from the needed information and skills needed in other to adequate be prepared for the future world of artificial intelligence and robotic society. Therefore, this paper conceptualize disabilities vis-à-vis how well they have related with digital technologies in this present time and thus provided template for institutions of higher learning on how well to prepare students with disabilities for the realities of Industrie 4.0.

Introduction

Since the introduction of the concept of fourth industrial revolution by Klaus Schwab, the concept have continually generate an unending discussion among stakeholders in the business, social, economic, political and even in the educational sector. The term 'forth industrial revolution', represent a new world that is technologically driven with a fundamental effect on human interaction, communication and quality of life. The revolution describes advanced digitalized networking between systems, process, machines and people involved in the process and output of value chain activities. Globally, the fourth industrial revolution (otherwise known as the Industrie 4.0) posed to influence and creates both desirable and undesirable changes to human interaction. According to Schwab (2017), the Industrie 4.0 is a revolutionary change delineated by the smaller, stronger and cheaper sensors, machine learning, artificial intelligence and robotic engineering as well as inescapable use and reliance on the Internet of Things. It is believed that the revolution will be largely driven by technologies to decentralize and automate management and leadership strategies, shared knowledge and experiences as well as access to and use of information. Interestingly, the influence of the Industrie 4.0 is currently evident in the present societies through rapid changes and processes at which information is harnessed, produced, processed, distributed and consumed through the instrument of Information, Communication and Technology devices.

Remarkably, human existence is highly susceptible to redefinition through the application of smart technologies capable of fostering efficiency and productivity of goods and services. Interestingly, the present society is a step into the future with the advent of initiated scientific and creative thinking potentials evident through the development and application of cloud computing, artificial intelligence, interactive robots, genetic engineering, internet of things, nanotechnology and development of assistive technologies designed to add value to human interaction and improve qualities of life (Jee, 2017). Hence, the society at present has continually benefited from the current and ongoing application of technologies which significantly and positively contributed to several observable changes in socio-economic and political contexts. Through this, it is expected that the future world of technology holds geometrical growth in how technologies will mediate the interactions and existence of human beings irrespective of abilities or disability status. In other words, persons with disabilities will share from all experiences presented by the Industrie 4.0. According to Delgado (2019), the future of technologies

holds a better life for persons with visual impairment with the possible integration of computerized enhanced vision applications with ultrasonic sensors, advanced augmentative and alternative communication for the deaf as well as an integration of electroencephalography-based brain-controlled approaches for individuals who are paraplegic. Hence, the technological revolution in its scope, complexities and scale tend to fundamentally change social integration, depletes family ties and social cohesion couple with a surge in new dimension of psychological and mental health disorders as society will largely depends on the internet rather than fostering of human-human interaction. However, Xu, David and Kim (2018) stated that the revolution could present high rate of social inequalities since human-human interactions is being replaced by machines, artificial intelligence and interactive robots. Therefore, there is a potential threat to low skilled and low wage jobs when such skills is digitalized or potential low skilled workers are replaced by robots and artificial intelligence. Although, while there is an eminent threat to jobs for low skilled workers, the future smart-society will require extensive application of cognitive and psychomotor abilities, a great deal of premium will be place on individuals with an in depth critically and logical thinking abilities. Unfortunately, increased dichotomization, through the indices of social inequalities may aggravate social tension, threats to life and properties, increased cybercrimes, hacking and advanced financial fraud.

Consequent upon the strengths of the fourth industrial revolution, Schwab (2015) as well as Xu, David and Kim (2018) commented and as well appreciated the threat posed by the techno-society. For instance, Xu and colleagues (2018) were greatly concerned by ethical issues of a techno-society. While Xu and colleagues were exited with the role of technologies in bio-engineering/technologies, infusion of machine in teaching and learning process, smarter society, the depletion in moral value and ethics remains a major concern. Similarly, Schwab (2015) revealed his fear about the fourth industrial revolution. Schwab's fear for the future is linked with the social inequalities, reduced social and human capital as well as dangers of unfiltered information shared over social media and loss of job to highly skilled and talented individuals while employers demand for the services of low skilled workers is decreased. Hence, this raised a serious concern for economic capacity of many especially persons with disabilities in the world of industrie 4.0. Consequently, in order to adequately prepare and combat the fear of the future, the World Economic Forum, the Presidential Commission on the Fourth Industrial Revolution in South Africa and academic at various fora have echo the need to salvage the fear of the future with the economic and political issues being at the center of such discussions. Unfortunately, previous discussions on the fourth industrial revolution have established the fear for the future with the neglects of persons with disabilities in their discussion towards the industrie 4.0. To this end, how persons with disability will effectively function in the technologically driven society remains a mirage and puzzle.

Conceptualizing and understanding disabilities

Issues on disability are long standing contentious and contested concepts. Its understanding has been argued by scholars in the field of disability studies, medical profession, sociologists, psychologist and many other professions. Its construct represents the loss or limitation by an individual to partake on an equal level with others in societal function due to environmental and social barriers. In other words, an individual with disabilities has physical or sensory impairment which has a long-term or substantial undesirable influence severe enough to prevent or impede one's ability to carry out day-to-day normal activities without necessary external supports. Persons with disability can be said to experience one or combination of difficulties in hearing, seeing, effective usage of the limbs, intellectual or learning disabilities, autism or cerebral palsy, speech defects and my other condition that negatively limits an individual in normal day-to-day engagements. According the description of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) (2006),

“persons with a disability are those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.”

As stated by WHO and World Bank (2011), over one billion or approximately fifteen per cent, out of the total population of the world live with some form of disability or the other. The 2011 estimate of the WHO and World Bank further revealed that about 110 million people (2.2%) have significant difficulty functioning, while 190 million (3.8%) have “severe disability”. Interestingly, while the world estimate was put at 15%, about 7.5 per cent of the South African population lives with one form of disability or the other. According to Lehohla (2014), the prevalence of disabilities in South Africa varies across the provinces but the percentage population of male with disabilities stands at 6.5 compared to 8.5% of South African females with disabilities (See Figure 1). Based on the report of Statistics South Africa, Lehohla (2014) assert that 11% of persons with disability had disorders with their sense of sight, 4.2% had difficulties with cognition, 3.6% had difficulties with the sense of hearing, while about 2% had difficulties with mobility, self-care and communication.

Figure 1: Graphical percentage representation of population of persons with disabilities in South Africa according to provinces computed by the author based on Statistics South Africa (2014).

As observed by Siebers (2008) and Delgado (2019), all the various forms of disabilities were perceived disability as a medical condition which must be eliminated or cured in order for an individual to achieve full potential like other members of the society whereas some students with hearing impairment in a study by Bell, Carl and Swart (2016) recognized the disadvantage of loss of sense of hearing, they described themselves as ‘normal’ who does not see themselves needing any medical intervention. Hence, the participants seem to be much concerned about their social integration than medical intervention. In other words, irrespective of disabling conditions, disability should be viewed within the context of human diversity. Therefore, the construct of disability need to be seen as a part of identity development, natural genetic variation (Ruby & Victoria, 2009) and not a deficit or problem that requires medical intervention but a social construct.

Over the years, studies of Lang (2007); Shakespeare (2010); Anastasiou and Kauffman (2013) as well as Retief and Letšosa (2018) have construed the social implication of disabilities through the social model rather than the medical perspectives. The social model of disability has given a need to critically denounced the proposition of medical perspectives towards disability because rather than seeing the limitation to function with the bio-physiological make-up of an individual, the social model, sees how individuals with disabilities are systematically oppressed, discriminated against and encounter negative attitude from other members of the society who lives without disabling conditions (Lang, 2007). For over a long period of time Barton (1996) remarked that have been faced with derogatory and pejorative societal attitude coupled with disdain, inhospitable and inaccessible physical environment, buildings and transportation systems which are unsuitable for the disabled.

Figure 2: Causative factors of disability with in the society

needs (*see figure 2*). The socio-political environment tends to have neglected the disabled population in their quest for a technosociety. The quest to shape public policies to accommodate the future through techno-skills has been discussed at the 2018 World Economic Forums towards the fourth industrial revolution as driver of social change is yet to fully integrate and consider the plight of the disabled population vis-à-vis their knowledge about the implication of information, communication and technology.

Disability and technological implications in the past and present

There is no gainsaying of the fact that, the millennium had offered humanity a great advantage through information and communication technologies (ICT). The influx of technological devices had crept into all spheres including but not limited to leisure, communication, industries, human resource management, aviation, medicine as well as education. However, while the benefit of technology is readily available to many, its accessibility and usage for social integration of persons with disability remains a concern. Irrespective of the concerns arising towards the relationship between technologies and disability, the detrimental effects of disabling conditions are sometimes masked by new technologies. According to Ford (2001), the implication of new technology creates opportunity for self-expression, inflate self-esteem and foster independence among users with disabled users. As stated by Guo et al. (2005) and Bowe (2007), persons with disabilities may have greatly benefited with the deployment and use of technological devices in employment, improve quality of life, healthcare and communication. Basically, Guo and colleagues noted that there is an increase in social interaction between the disabled and their immediate social environment via virtual space communication. Nonetheless, it may also result into additional disability in some circumstances (Goggin and Newell, 2003; Ellis and Kent, 2011; Al Zidjaly 2015). In their 2003 study Goggin and Newell (2003) expressed their dissatisfaction with how technology designers, create high-tech and expensive technologies with the mind of alleviating challenges posed by disabling condition but in the other way round contributing to emotional, physical and economic difficulties among the disabled, largely because, the end users are not usually incorporated during assistive device production processes. With regards to the various perceived role of technology (tangible/virtual, low/high, cheap/expensive) on the functionality of persons with disabilities, various arguments in academic, clinical and career sphere have been much concerned with bodily condition than social capacities and how the disabled will function independently in the social sphere or its extent of use, enthusiasm towards adoption and use as well as inconveniences of usage among the end users.

Technology has opened new horizons with a great potential for social and political identities of the disabled, but it also holds the potential to alienate members of the society with disability when psycho-contextual factors such as age, gender, severity of disability, marketisation of technology, aids and equipment, perception and experience (Chaves et al., 2004) as well as technological accessibility, adoption and usage is not put into consideration. Despite the promising and evident opportunities of technology for the disabled, barrier towards its adoption and use is still very visible with the society. According to Van Dijk (1999), adoption of technology for use among persons with disabilities is closely associated with the interest, attractiveness and motivation to using the technology as well as capacity to skillfully manipulate the acquired technology for an individuals' advantage. In line with the proposition of the social model of disability, Oliver (1990) and the European Commission (2007) remarked that new technologies may not in the immediate appeal to persons with disabilities because of either or both of personal or socioeconomic factors. The submission of the European Commission clearly substantiates to past revelation of the National Council on Disability (2001) and D'Aubin (2007) who had previously reported that persons with disabilities who were in dire need of technological support lives on a very low income than others and therefore are poor with less financial capabilities to acquire and use necessary assistive technological devices. Additionally, the level of poverty found within among persons with disabilities is not extremely because of their disabling condition but because of experienced negative societal attitude, marginalization and lack of access or adequate opportunities to access quality education. Hence, many individuals with disability may not be able to afford the cost of assistive technologies and the capability to use and maintain or upgrade them. Against the fact that assistive devices are expensive and not easy to maintain, policy issues and political will was described by the Royal National Institute of Blind People et al. (2005) as a major determinant factor that impede the progress in the use of technology towards achieving an inclusive society. While the Royal National Institute of Blind People et al. had accused the political class for the extent of technological use by the disabled, Jones in a 2016 Caribbean study which assessed the use of information and communication technology by the disabled, clearly indicated that the potential to use technology by the disabled is largely occasioned by the type and severity of their disabilities with a resultant effects on the standard or living, work and family life. Hence, the existing and available literature including that of Duplaga (2017) provided evidence that persons with disabilities at his current time are still overshadowed by the digital divides and are yet to fully comprehend the use of technology for use for an inclusive society.

Persons with disability now and the future techno-society

The expectation of researchers in academic, clinical, economic and the political class is that the future will largely be automated. Its automation of work place and industries is expected to positively drive the economy

but not with a consequence on human-human interaction, psychosocial wellbeing and quality of life. Although, while there is a palpable fear of job loss due to several low skilled job or routine jobs being takeover by machine, robots and artificial intelligence, persons without disabilities have currently being scaling up their skills in other not to be caught by unemployment in the future fourth industrial revolution. While many skills development programmes is being organized across the globe, such programme seem to have neglected persons with disabilities. In fact, various high discussions, especially at the World Economic Forum regarding the future techno-society have underplayed the importance of critically engaging persons with disabilities so as to fully function in the world driven by technology. Hence, this intellectual piece therefore encourages stakeholders in education, the political elites, parents and non-profit organizations to include in their discussion the plight of persons with disabilities in the Industrie 4.0. Moreso, researches that will create better understanding of the technological needs of persons with disabilities should be instituted. Importantly, such investigations should avoid the exclusion of the end users in their research. The research should ensure to determine what, when, how and where of assistive technologies. In other words, cultures and geographical divides should be taken into consideration in the development and deployment of assistive technologies for the disabled. There should be conscious effort of all stakeholders driving the need to prepare for the fourth industrial revolution to contribute to creating of activities that will close gaps created by digital knowledge. This implies that awareness about the importance of having skills in information and communication technology among persons with disabilities. More so, educators at all levels should drive a technologically inclined teaching and learning processes. Course or module contents should provoke creativity skills and encourages learners with disabilities to critically think towards solving a potential societal problem. Classrooms environment should be stimulating and arouse learners' curiosity to quest for more knowledge. Hence, government at all levels needs to scale up their budget in educational sector in other for the school and resources rooms to be fully equipped with technological facilities that responds to any form of disabilities with which such classroom or facilities is designed for. Behavioural researchers, psychologist, parents of persons with disabilities and special educators should at all time to educate the society about the imminent dangers of alienating the disables. Persons without disabilities should be encouraged to positively relate, interact and provide necessary assistance to individuals with disabilities. Training opportunities in technological skills needed to effectively function in the future techno-society should be regularly organized for the disabled. Such training should involve the manufactures of assistive technologies who will educate the users of the implication of any assistive technology used by the disabled. Suitable policies that will facilitate the adoption and effective use of technology by persons with disabilities should be enshrined with all legislative support. Above all, the ability of anyone with disability to use and positively manipulate or engage information and communication technology for the development of humanity should be appreciated and adequate support should be equally given.

Conclusion

This paper have examined and dissected the intricacies fourth industrial revolution (otherwise known as Industrie 4.0) as well as its implication on the future society which is believed to be governed by technology. This paper appreciated the role of technology in this present time and what the future of technology holds for all. The nature of disability was exposed via the social model of discussing disabling conditions as well as the present situation of access to technology adoption of technology and its usage among persons with disability. While this paper observed that access to technology, its adoption and usage is dependent on the type and severity of disability, this study therefore brought to the fore, the need to actively awaken technological curiosity and use among persons with this ability through various instrument of community engagement and policy enactment.

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